

Ethics in IT

Ethical Implications and Challenges of Autonomous Driving on Society and Company Autonomous Cars Inc.

A RESEARCH CASE STUDY

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AV	Autonomous Vehicles
AI	Artificial Intelligence

ABSTRACT

With the advent of digital age in artificial intelligence, new challenges for the ethics in IT are introduced. In the digital global village, everyone is affected with new technologies. In a civilized cyber world, Positive use of IT referred as Ethics in IT. Autonomous vehicles is one the great discovery of artificial intelligence. Rapid development in use of the autonomous vehicles introducing the challenges for society and manufacturers. These challenges and implications are related to increase safety concerns, more public trust, ethical dilemmas in decision making in the inevitable accidents, lack of rules and regulations for testing the autonomous vehicle, more need of research in ethical programming, communication and collaboration gap between researcher ,society and manufacturers ,mass unemployment and inapplicable for underdeveloped countries. To find the accountability for the actions of autonomous vehicles and necessary changes in programming, a detailed literature review conducted. In existing literature, reveals that the accountability aspect for the actions of autonomous vehicle is not address, moreover the need of programming changes is still need more research. This research study emphasizes on extensive study of ethical implications and challenges of autonomous driving on society and the manufacturer. It provides detailed comparative analysis of pros and cons of autonomous driving for all the stack holders of the autonomous vehicles. This study answers about the accountability of actions by autonomous vehicles and need of changes in programming by conducting literature review and comparative analysis. The result of the case study shows that the manufacturer is responsible for the actions of autonomous vehicles and the new modes of ethical programming can overcome the most demanding challenges.

Keyword- Autonomous vehicles, Testing, Regulations, Deontological Rule, Consequentialism, Moral Machine, Intelligent Transportation System, Ethical Dilemma , Algorithm ,Decision Making

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

This chapter deals with an introduction of the Ethics in IT specifically autonomous driving challenges and implications over society and the manufacturer. This chapter describes the importance of ethical concerns for all the stack holders of autonomous driving. At the end of this chapter, the problem and the methodology of finding and analyzing the impact of autonomous driving challenges and implications over society and the company autonomous cars Inc. discussed.

1.1 Background of Case Study

The rapid advancement of IT and artificial intelligence introduced ethical questions, especially in autonomous driving. The case study is about "Autonomous Cars Inc.," a leading light in self-driving vehicles. Despite the company's commitment to safety, an accident raises ethical concerns. The incident prompts questions about responsibility for the autonomous vehicle's actions. Should Autonomous Cars Inc. Accountable for the accident and should the vehicle's programming prioritize pedestrian safety over occupants? The ethical challenges extend to algorithmic bias, data protection, and potential impacts on employment in the transportation sector, prompting a comprehensive evaluation of ethical implications in autonomous driving.

Through this study, the researcher will try to find the answers of these questions. This is an effort to study whether the ethical implications and challenges of autonomous driving on society and the company Autonomous Cars Inc. influence to attainment of successful and sustainable ethics in self driving. The present study tries to describe the ethical implications and challenges of autonomous driving on society and the company Autonomous Cars Inc. Besides, it strains to answer the above-mentioned questions. Thus, it put forward some implications to the researchers of the company Autonomous Cars Inc. Consequently, it surprises with comparative analysis of advantages and disadvantages of self-driving cars for society, manufacturer and researchers.

1.2 Ethics in IT

Ethics in IT refers to the rules or principals required for the ethical behavior that result the positive use of technology. The **ethics in IT** is a sub-field of ethics addressing the ethical questions specific to the information technology, the transitional shift in society wherein personal computers and subsequent devices provide for the quick and easy transfer of information. Technology ethics is the application of ethical thinking to the growing concerns of new technologies continue to rise in prominence (Reynolds, G., 2009).

Ethics in IT is more about considering the factors such as the values, moral principles, and rules of conduct, ethical practices rules, and regulations regional and religion believes of a society. Therefore, the ethical implications and challenges of autonomous driving on society and manufacturer are result of above-mentioned factor.

FIGURE 1.1 Factors Affecting The Ethics in IT

1.2.1 Rational for Study

Through this study, we theoretically seek to understand the ethical implications and challenges of autonomous driving on society and the manufacturers and answer the questions; Who is responsible for the actions of the autonomous vehicles? Should the manufacturer of the vehicle ,Autonomous Cars Inc., be held responsible for the accident? Should the programming of the autonomous vehicle be changed to ensure that it always protects pedestrians, even if this endangers the occupants?

1.2.2 Motivation for Case Study

In this case study research, our motivations are to research into the ethical surrounding autonomous driving technology. The rapid advancement of autonomous vehicles, as our case study about 'Autonomous Cars Inc.,' that gives an insight of the responsibilities associated with their actions. The study aims to address important questions regarding accountability and focusing on the manufacturer's role, in this case, Autonomous Cars Inc. Additionally, the examination extends to the ethical considerations involved in programming decisions, exploring whether prioritizing pedestrian safety over occupants is a viable solution. By dealing with these issues, we aim to contribute to the concepts of the ethical challenges modelled by autonomous driving and encourage the researchers, ethically strong development and deployment practices.

1.3 Case Study Organization

Chapter 2 surveys the existing literature about ethical implications and challenges of autonomous driving on society and the manufacturers, gap analysis and problem statement, also describes the methodology that are for the proposed solution. Chapter 3 gives the results of the comparative analysis and summaries and concludes the whole case study briefly. Chapter 4 gives all the bibliography in APA style.

CHAPTER 2

MAIN PART

In this chapter, we have conducted a detailed study about the ethical implications and challenges of autonomous driving on society and the manufacturers. The company "Autonomous Cars Inc." is involved in an accident in which a person dies. This literature review will help us to answer the questions that arise after the accident. Moreover, in this chapter the research design as specifically designed for present study has been produced which comprises problem of statement, the proposed solution, comparative analysis of advantages and disadvantages of autonomous driving.

2.1 Review of Literature

Detjen, D. *et al.* (2023), proposed a way to handle these dilemmas by making the self-driving cars adapt their decisions to minimize harm. It suggests using a system called a Markov decision process to help the cars decide what to do. The cars would pick actions based on how much harm they might cause to different people like passengers, pedestrians, cyclists, and other drivers. This paper shows that self-driving cars can change their paths based on ethical evaluations, not just in emergencies but also during regular driving.

Hutchin, *et al.* (2017) As self-driving systems become more common, there's a growing need to focus on the ethics of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Autonomous Systems (AS). People are curious about how these programs will make ethical choices and handle moral issues during development. Currently, developers mainly make these choices based on their personal views, leading to discussions about how to handle challenging situations objectively. Many worry about how AI/AS systems make ethical decisions, leading to a desire for human involvement. The IEEE Standards Association is working on guidelines to address these concerns, and this paper reviews these guidelines, exploring various situations that could pose social and ethical challenges in AI/AS development

In (Islam, *et al.*, 2018) authors discussed how to make autonomous cars more common, manufacturers must face an important ethical challenge related to decision-making algorithms. When accident is unavoidable, self-driving vehicles face critical decision involving multiple lives. This article introduces a programming approach using a visualized algorithm, employing a priority queue-based min-heap sorting system. The algorithm prioritizes lives based on certain parameters and includes terms like "probability of survival." Its flexibility allows customers and manufacturers to customize ethical decisions according to their values.

In (Narayanan, *et al.*, 2019) author discussed a way to use fuzzy control in machine ethics. The paper shows how researcher can build a system that decides when it is morally okay to take over from a

human driver. The good about this approach is that it can learn its own moral rules, reducing the chance of picking up human biases and prejudices.

In (Tho, *et al.*, 2019) presented indicators related to the operational environment, crucial for fostering cooperation in car navigation behavior. Additionally, the authors give the necessity of a robust input variable model to improve the decision-making capacity of autonomous vehicles in emergencies. Through a comprehensive analysis, this paper contributes valuable insights to the ongoing discourse on ethical and legal challenges in autonomous vehicle technology.

In (Wang, *et al.*, 2020) authors presented those ethical concerns that are hurdle in adoption of autonomous vehicles. Despite the development of machine ethics over several decades, ethical decision-making in autonomous driving presents complicated and developing challenges. The paper critically examines the dedicated efforts made by academia, policymakers, and automakers in recent years to address these challenges. However, the review highlights the absence of a universal solution encourage author to offer recommendations aimed at development collaboration among society, manufacturer and researchers to effectively address the remaining ethical dilemmas.

2.2 Statement of Problem

Existing literature not provided or partially provided the ethical implications and challenges of autonomous driving on society and the manufacturers.

Autonomous Vehicles (AVs) have the potential of significantly increase safety and transportation efficiency (Shariff, *et al.*, 2017). It is necessary to understand the advantages and disadvantages of autonomous so the challenges and implications of autonomous driving on society and manufacturers Driver less cars are becoming most popular in the world and is passing through the transformation phase from human base driving to the autonomous driving by artificial intelligence. In this regard, more ethical IT infrastructure establishment has become now the dominant and leading issue for discussion among scholars, international autonomous driving manufacturers, investors and social scholars in the similar field. However, the creativities for realizing worthy autonomous vehicles infrastructure not initiated equally in its true spirit around globe particularly developing countries. The concept of "Ethics in IT " is very popular concept and many countries are adopting this concept to describe the ethical implications and challenges of autonomous driving on society and the manufacturers.

The problems addressed in this study are relate with the ethical implications and challenges of autonomous driving on society and the manufacturers and answer the questions; who is responsible for the actions of the autonomous vehicles? Should the manufacturer of the vehicle, Autonomous Cars Inc., is held responsible for the accident? Should the programming of the autonomous vehicle changed to

ensure that it always protects pedestrians, even if this endangers the occupants? This is main reason why researcher has selected the said topic to research.

2.2.1 Research Questions

Our research is about finding the ethical implications and challenges of autonomous driving on society and the manufacturers. However, the following issues for the company Autonomous Cars Inc. must consider:

RQ1. Who is responsible for the actions of the autonomous vehicles?

RQ2. Should the manufacturer of the vehicle, Autonomous Cars Inc., is held responsible for the accident?

RQ3. Should the programming of the autonomous vehicle changed to ensure that it always protects pedestrians, even if this endangers the occupants.

2.3 Ethical Implications and Challenges of Autonomous Driving

After detailed review of literature following ethical implications and challenges of autonomous driving on society and manufacturer the company Autonomous Cars Inc. are as follows:

2.3.1 Challenge of Decision Making

Autonomous vehicles (AV) are one of the greater revolution for the transportation industry. Safety is the biggest factor that is associated with transportation.

Autonomous vehicles face ethical dilemmas in decision making during unavoidable accidents. Questions arise about how vehicles prioritize safety, especially when there is a situation where passengers, pedestrians, cyclists and other drivers.

2.3.2 Challenge of Responsibility and Accountability

Human driver is responsible for the safe journey but in case of accident, many factors are also considered. In case of driver less vehicles, this responsibility goes towards the software of the vehicle.

Determining accountability for accidents involving autonomous vehicles raises ethical questions. Should the manufacturer, in this case, Autonomous Cars Inc., be held responsible for accidents, and how should liability be addressed?

2.3.3 Algorithmic Implications

Software of self-driving cars have a risk of making them biased without intentions. This means they might treat different groups of people unfairly. To do implement the algorithm ethically, a hard decision under the detailed public survey insights is required.

2.3.4 Challenge of Public Trust

The incidence of Trolley problem, the typical dilemma scenario of the trolley problem is: a runaway trolley is about to run over four human who are standing on the tracks inadvertently. Another dilemma, called self-sacrifice, can confronted by AVs. Third dilemma is unexpected animals a typical accident involving unexpected animals indicates the complexity of the decision-making facing the AVs (Wang, *et al.*, 2020). These incidents involving autonomous vehicles can affect public trust. Ethical challenges include building and maintaining public confidence, addressing concerns, and transparently communicating about the safety and ethical considerations of autonomous driving.

2.3.5 Challenge of New Rules and Regulation

Autonomous driving needs rules and regulations by the country. It is a great challenge for the policy makers to find the ethical solutions for the autonomous vehicles manufacturers. Manufacturers must navigate ethical considerations related to following the rules, ensuring safety, and contributing to the development of responsible guidelines.

2.3.6 Challenge of Economic Growth and Unemployment

The more adoption of autonomous vehicles may have implications for jobs in the transportation sector. Ethical considerations involve addressing the chance of having more jobless drivers. The manufacturers can gain a lot of profit but the employment rate can go down.

2.3.7 Environmental and Social Impact

Autonomous Vehicles and human driven vehicles is an ethical challenge. Addressing how autonomous vehicles communicate their intentions to human drivers and pedestrians involves ethical considerations to enhance safety. Autonomous driving affect the environment and society by minimizing environmental harm, reducing traffic jam, and ensuring that autonomous driving contributes positively to societal wellbeing.

2.4 Proposed Solution

In social research there are various approaches recommended by researchers to access population of the study. In this regard, survey approach has recommended as best approach to access the population of the research study. In social research, there are two recommended sources of data collection, among

which one is secondary data and the 2nd is primary data. However, the primary data was collected through the structured questionnaire, which developed with the collaboration of the XYZ survey bureau and analysts and after their recommendations; the questionnaire was distributed in the field study.

TABLE 2.1 Respondents views about the Statement

Who is responsible for the actions of the autonomous vehicles? The company Autonomous Cars Inc. is responsible.					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Agree	96	57.8	57.8	57.8
	Neutral	42	25.3	25.3	83.1
	Disagree	28	16.9	16.9	100.0
	Total	166	100.0	100.0	

The above table shows the frequencies of responses concerning the statement of who is responsible for the actions of the autonomous vehicles and its answer that the company is responsible. In this regard, 96 (57.8%) respondents were agreed with above answer, 42 (25.3%) respondents were neutral while 28 (16.9%) respondents were disagree with the said answer. Thus, most of the respondents were of the opinion that The Company Autonomous Cars Inc. is responsible for the actions of the autonomous vehicles.

TABLE 2.2 Respondents observations about the Statement

Should the manufacturer of the vehicle, Autonomous Cars Inc., is held responsible for the accident?					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Agree	76	45.8	45.8	45.8
	Neutral	52	31.3	31.3	77.1
	Disagree	38	22.9	22.9	100.0
	Total	166	100.0	100.0	

The table above shows the frequencies with regard to the responses of respondents concerning the statement that should the manufacturer of the vehicle, Autonomous Cars Inc., is held responsible for the accident. For this drive, 76 (45.8%) respondents were agree who supported said statement, 52 (31.3%) respondents were neutral while 38 (22.9%) respondents were disagree about the said

statement. Therefore, most of respondents were agree that the manufacturer of the vehicle, Autonomous Cars Inc., is held responsible for the accident.

TABLE 2.3 Respondents opinion about the Statement

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Agree	120	72.3	72.3	72.3
	Neutral	30	18.1	18.1	90.4
	Disagree	16	9.6	9.6	100.0
	Total	166	100.0	100.0	

The frequencies table above shows that there were 120 (72.3%) respondents who were agree to the statement should the programming of the autonomous vehicle changed to ensure that it always protects pedestrians, even if this endangers the occupants. Similarly, 30 (18.1%) respondents were neutral about the said statement while 16 (9.6%) respondents were disagree with the said statement. Therefore, from the responses, it becomes clear that most of the respondents agreed that the programming of the autonomous vehicle should changed to ensure that it always protects pedestrians, even if this endangers the occupants.

Various public responses about ethical implications of self-driving shown in Figure 2.1.

FIGURE 2.1 Public Response about Ethical Implications of Self-Driving

(Bonnefon, et al., 2016)

CHAPTER 3

CONCLUSION

This case study concludes from the hints of the previous studies and from the results of the present study that the ethical implications and challenges of autonomous vehicles on society and manufacturer are need to address. Moreover, Autonomous Cars Inc. is responsible for the actions of the autonomous vehicles. The manufacturer of the vehicle, Autonomous Cars Inc. should be held responsible for the accident. The programming of the autonomous vehicle should be change to ensure that it always protects pedestrians, even if this endangers the occupants.

3.1 Summary

Rapid development in use of the autonomous vehicles introducing the challenges for society and manufacturers. These challenges and implications are related to increase safety concerns, more public trust, ethical dilemmas in decision making in the inevitable accidents, lack of rules and regulations for testing the autonomous vehicle, more need of research in ethical programming, communication and collaboration gap between researcher ,society and manufacturers ,mass unemployment and inapplicable for underdeveloped countries. To find the accountability for the actions of autonomous vehicles and necessary changes in programming, a detailed literature review conducted. This research study surveys with the questioner. This study answers about the accountability of actions by autonomous vehicles and need of changes in programming by conducting literature review and comparative analysis. The result of the case study shows that the manufacturer is responsible for the actions of autonomous vehicles and the ethical programming can overcome the most demanding challenges.

3.3 Conclusion and Future Work

After successful completion of case study, we plan to conduct surveys using forums that are more famous. The country wise ethical implications and challenges of autonomous driving on society and the manufacturers can be find out.

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Annexure 1 Questionnaire

Ethical Implications and Challenges of Autonomous Driving on Society and Company Autonomous Cars Inc.

A Case Study of Autonomous Cars Inc.

Mr. Emmanuel

International University of Applied Science

Respondents Profile

Age: _____

Residence: _____

Education: _____

Designation: _____

Gender: _____

Department: _____

Note: Agreement/Disagreement with the Statements by using **3-point Scale?**

Question No. 1: Who is responsible for the actions of the autonomous vehicles?

Agreement	Neutral	Disagreement
1	2	3

Question No. 2: Should the manufacturer of the vehicle, Autonomous Cars Inc., is held responsible for the accident?

Agreement	Neutral	Disagreement
1	2	3

Question No. 3: Should the programming of the autonomous vehicle changed to ensure that it always protects pedestrians, even if this endangers the occupants.

Agreement	Neutral	Disagreement
1	2	3